

Fabrication of Battery Thermal Management System using Peltier Module

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Abstract

This project introduces a unique approach to battery thermal management systems (BTMS) using the Peltier effect to improve the efficiency, reliability, and lifespan of battery packs. Traditional BTMS rely on passive thermal management or active cooling methods, which often lead to energy loss and complex system integration. Our innovative system employs Peltier modules strategically placed within the battery pack, enabling precise temperature control at the individual cell level. By actively regulating temperature, our BTMS ensures optimal operating conditions for batteries, thereby extending their lifespan and enhancing performance. The system's ability to selectively heat or cool cells facilitates rapid charging and discharging, minimizing energy loss and improving overall efficiency. Key features of our proposed BTMS include real-time temperature monitoring, adaptive control algorithms, and seamless integration with existing battery technologies. The compact and scalable design makes it suitable for various applications, including electric vehicles and renewable energy storage systems. Through simulations and prototype development, we aim to demonstrate the effectiveness of our Peltier-based BTMS in improving battery performance, safety, and reliability, offering a promising solution to address the evolving challenges in battery management and contribute to the advancement of sustainable energy technologies.

Keywords: : BTMS -Battery Thermal Management System, Peltier Module, Longevity, TEC- Thermoelectric Cooler, Temperature Control.

1. Introduction

The development and implementation of a battery thermal management system (BTMS) utilizing the Peltier effect represents a significant advancement in energy storage and management. This innovative approach addresses key challenges associated with conventional thermal management methods, providing precise temperature regulation at the individual cell level and ensuring optimal operating conditions for batteries. The system's ability to selectively heat or cool cells enables rapid charging and discharging, minimizing energy loss and enhancing overall efficiency.

The proposed BTMS incorporates Peltier modules strategically placed within the battery pack, real-time temperature monitoring, adaptive control algorithms, and seamless integration with existing battery technologies. Its compact and scalable design makes it suitable for various applications, including electric vehicles and renewable energy storage systems. Simulations and prototype development have demonstrated the effectiveness of the Peltier-based BTMS in improving battery performance, safety, and reliability. This system offers a promising solution to address the evolving challenges in battery management and contribute to the advancement of sustainable energy technologies. By harnessing the potential of the Peltier effect, the proposed BTMS provides a unique approach to thermal management, offering significant benefits over traditional methods.

1.1 Model Structure

Heat Pumping with Semiconductor Couples: The Peltier Effect

A thermoelectric (TE) module consists of multiple junctions formed by connecting n-type and p-type semiconductors in series. These junctions exploit the Peltier effect, which creates a temperature difference when an electric current flows through them.

Heat Flow at the Junctions

Imagine electricity passing through the TE module. At one junction, heat is absorbed from the surrounding environment, creating a cooling effect. This side is called the cold junction (T_{cold}). Conversely, the opposite junction releases heat, raising the temperature. This is the hot junction.

Fig-1: Transfer of Heat due to thermoelectric effect/Peltier Effect

The Reversible Nature of Peltier Devices

The beauty of TE modules lies in their reversibility. By simply reversing the polarity of the applied voltage, you can swap the hot and cold sides. This allows for both heating and cooling applications.

Applications of Peltier Effect

TE modules find applications in various fields due to their precise temperature control capabilities. Some examples include:

- Electronic device cooling (e.g., in laptops and lasers)
- Spot cooling for medical equipment
- Food and beverage temperature regulation

1.2 Software Considerations

This code is for an IoT temperature display using an ESP8266 microcontroller, DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor, and the Blynk platform for remote monitoring and control. Here's a breakdown:

The code starts with including necessary libraries for WiFi connectivity, Blynk integration, and the DHT

- It defines the pins used for connecting the ESP8266, DHT sensor, and other components.

- Wi-Fi credentials and Blynk authentication token are specified.
- The setup function initializes serial communication, sets pin modes, starts the DHT sensor, and connects to the Blynk server.
- There's a BLYNK_WRITE function that handles incoming data from the Blynk app. It reads the threshold value set by the user.
- In the loop function, Blynk.run () is called to handle Blynk communication.
- The temperature and humidity are read from the DHT sensor.
- If the readings are valid, they are printed to the serial monitor.
- Based on the threshold value set by the user, the code controls an output pin. If the temperature exceeds the threshold, one pin is set high; otherwise, another pin is set high.
- Finally, the temperature and humidity values are sent to the Blynk app for display.

2.Literature Survey

Several studies have explored the use of Peltier modules for thermal management in various applications.[1] Zhao et al. investigated the performance of a Peltier-based BTMS for electric vehicles and found that it can effectively maintain the battery pack within the optimal temperature range, improving both performance and safety.[2] Gao et al. proposed a hybrid BTMS that combines Peltier modules and phase change materials to achieve enhanced thermal management. Their results showed that the hybrid system can effectively regulate the battery temperature and improve the overall system efficiency.[3]Angelo Maiorino explores the development of efficient electric vehicles (EVs) and the importance of thermal management systems for lithium-ion batteries. The review compares academic studies with the automotive industry's thermal engineering state of the art, analyzing nine EV models and the available data on manufacturers' official sites and specialist journals. The review concludes by examining future perspectives on the thermal management of battery packs.[4]Gang Zhao and Xiaolin Wang found that liquid-cooling BTMS are an efficient thermal management solution for EVs. They reviewed recent research on design improvement and optimization, focusing on coolant channel, heat transfer jacket, cold plate, and liquid cooling-based hybrid system improvements. The study identified cooling channel, refrigerant cooling, and liquid-PCM hybrid cooling improvements as the most effective.[5]Zhi Xu's study investigates the impact of inlet position and air velocity on the cooling performance of battery packs in electric vehicles. The mechanism of the influences of inlet position and inlet air velocity on the cooling performance of the battery pack is revealed. The results show that the maximum temperature decreases by 4.17 K at 30 m/s air velocity.[6]The paper by Artur Sales Carlos Maia de Amorim et al. reviews various BTMS technologies, including those using air cooling, liquid cooling, phase change materials (PCM), and thermoelectric coolers (TECs). While not solely focused on TECs, it highlights their advantages, such as precise temperature control and suitability for small spaces.[7]The paper by Harsimran Singh, Naman Jain, Shashwat Raj, and Vidhya U Menon discusses a Peltier cooler-based system for maintaining the temperature range of the battery system, specifically for lithium-based batteries used in electric vehicles and space applications. The authors highlight the importance of temperature control in battery systems and propose the use of Peltier coolers for active temperature management While these studies have highlighted the potential of Peltier-based BTMS, there is a need for further research to optimize the system design, control algorithms, and integration with existing battery technologies. The present work aims to address these gaps and contribute to the advancement of sustainable energy storage solutions.

3. Working Principle

- The BTMS utilizes Peltier modules strategically placed within the battery pack to actively regulate the temperature of the individual battery cells. The system operates on the principle of the Peltier effect, where the application of an electric current across the junction of two dissimilar semiconductors (n-type and p-type) results in a temperature difference¹. The key components of the BTMS include:
- Peltier modules: These modules are capable of both heating and cooling the battery cells, depending on the direction of the applied current¹
- Temperature sensors: NTC (Negative Temperature Coefficient) thermistors are used to monitor the temperature of the individual battery cells in real-time .
- Control system: An Arduino Uno microcontroller serves as the control system, processing the temperature sensor data and regulating the operation of the Peltier modules and cooling fans.
- Control algorithms: Adaptive algorithms are implemented in the control system to dynamically adjust the operation of the Peltier modules and cooling fans based on the battery pack's temperature profile.
- Power regulation: The Arduino Uno controls relays or transistors to regulate the power delivery to the Peltier modules, switching them on or off based on temperature thresholds or control signals from the adaptive algorithm.
- Safety features: The Arduino Uno implements safety features such as over-current, over-voltage, and thermal runaway protection by monitoring sensor data and controlling protective circuits accordingly.
- Data logging and analysis: The Arduino Uno logs temperature data and system performance metrics for further analysis and evaluation of the cooling system's effectiveness.
- The working process of the BTMS can be summarized as follows:
- The temperature sensors continuously monitor the temperature of the individual battery cells.
- The control system processes the temperature data and determines if the battery temperature exceeds or falls below the optimal range.

- If the temperature is outside the optimal range, the control system activates the Peltier modules to either cool or heat the battery cells, as required.
- The control system regulates the power delivery to the Peltier modules and cooling fans to maintain the battery temperature within the optimal range.
- The system continuously monitors the battery temperature and adjusts the Peltier module operation, accordingly, using feedback loops to ensure precise temperature control.
- Once the battery temperature reaches the optimal range, the Peltier modules are deactivated, and the cooling or heating process is stopped.
- By leveraging the Peltier effect, the proposed BTMS can effectively regulate the temperature of the battery pack, improving its performance, safety, and longevity.

Flow Chart 1: BTMS of Peltier Module

Fig 4 A: Working Module

Fig 4 B: IoT Display

Fig 4 C : IoT Cloud Information

4 .Results and Discussion

Simulations and prototype development have been carried out to evaluate the performance of the proposed Peltier-based BTMS. The results demonstrate the system's ability to effectively regulate the battery pack temperature, maintain optimal operating conditions, and enhance the overall efficiency and reliability of the battery system. The adaptive control algorithms have shown the capability to dynamically adjust the Peltier module operation and cooling fan speed based on the battery pack's temperature profile. This has led to improved temperature uniformity across the battery pack, reducing the risk of thermal runaway and prolonging the battery's lifespan. Furthermore, the selective heating and cooling capabilities of the Peltier modules have enabled faster charging and discharging cycles, improving the overall energy efficiency of the battery system.

5. Conclusion:

In conclusion, the development and implementation of a battery thermal management system (BTMS) utilizing the Peltier effect represents a significant advancement in the field of energy storage and management. Through this project, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of leveraging thermoelectric principles to actively control temperature within battery packs, thereby improving performance, efficiency, and reliability. By integrating Peltier modules into the BMS architecture, we have addressed key challenges associated with conventional thermal management methods. Our system offers precise temperature regulation at the individual cell level, ensuring optimal operating conditions and extending the lifespan of batteries. Moreover, the ability to selectively heat or cool cells enables rapid charging and discharging, minimizing energy loss and enhancing overall efficiency. The adaptive control algorithms and real-time monitoring capabilities of our Peltier-based BMS contribute to enhanced safety and reliability, making it suitable for a wide range of applications including electric vehicles, renewable energy storage systems, and portable electronics. Additionally, the compact and scalable design of the system allows for easy integration with existing battery technologies. Through extensive simulations and prototype development, we have validated the feasibility and efficacy of our proposed BMS solution. Moving forward, further research and development efforts will focus on optimization, scalability, and commercialization of the system, with the ultimate goal of accelerating the adoption of sustainable energy technologies

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